

The influence of cross-section variation on bending stiffness assessment in existing timber structures

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Abstract

The frequent highly irregular geometry of the elements in existing timber structures complicates the structural verification of members and influences the use of non-destructive testing (NDT), affecting the inspection time, cost and results obtained. This process therefore needs to be improved. The main aim of this paper is to analyse how to obtain a representative nominal cross-section (NCS) of members, and its influence on determination of the static modulus of elasticity (MOE_{sta}). 21 150x200x11000 mm³ Salzmänn pine (*Pinus nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* (Dunal) Franco) timber rafters from the 18th century Royal Coliseum of Charles III theatre (in Aranjuez, Madrid, Spain) were acoustically tested (by ultrasound, stress wave and vibration). The MOE_{sta} was determined by mechanical testing, and different criteria for determining the NCS were analysed. Good correlation was obtained between the MOE_{sta} and NDT parameters, and the best criterion to assign NCS was proposed to improve the accuracy of the models obtained by reducing the number of NCS measurements.

Key words

Existing timber structures, geometric variability, non-destructive testing, ultrasound, stress wave, vibration.

1. Introduction

Most of the studies using non-destructive testing (NDT) on timber pieces to estimate their mechanical properties centre on new sawn timber or small specimens. In recent years, *in-situ* building assessments have been complemented with the use of NDT such as stress waves, ultrasound, vibration, probing, and visual strength grading (VSG) to determine the physical and mechanical properties of existing structural timber members [1–8]. NDT research has led to new portable devices and methodologies, which have given rise to very positive results and new research lines [9]. This makes it possible to accurately estimate relevant parameters such as density, modulus of elasticity (MOE), and strength values, using the models described in research works for various species. These models allow safe verification of members from existing structures to estimate their bearing capacity or to identify biotic and structural damage [10–15].

Some research work conclusions are presented below using the above-mentioned NDTs:

1.1 Visual Strength Grading

VSG of timber for structural use can be used to establish a strength class depending on species and their physical-mechanical properties. Arriaga et al. [2] showed that there are no significant differences between the mechanical properties of pieces with or without waness due to the continuity of surface fibres in 84 test pieces from existing structures (52 Scots pine [*Pinus sylvestris* L.] and 32 maritime pine [*Pinus pinaster* Ait.] pieces). Arriaga et al. [16] carried out VSG of 395 sawn timber pieces of three species (Scots pine, Salzmänn pine [*Pinus nigra* subsp.

salzmannii (Dunal) Franco] and radiata pine [*Pinus radiata* D. Don]) according to the UNE 56544 [17] Spanish standard. 52% of pieces were rejected. The percentage of rejected pieces was reduced to 10% by only considering knots and grain slope, with no significant differences in mechanical properties. Esteban et al. [3] related the fissures on timber with shear strength, MOE and modulus of rupture (MOR) using mechanical tests, concluding that there is no significant relationship between fissures and mechanical properties.

1.2 Combining VSG and NDT

Other research works have combined VSG and NDT with positive results. Cavalli et al. [18] showed prediction values of the static modulus of elasticity (MOE_{sta}) through the dynamic modulus of elasticity (MOE_{dyn}) and wane parameter with $r^2 = 0.70$ and MOR with $r^2 = 0.43$ in 81 Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.) and Silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.) pieces from existing structures. In addition, two trusses from an existing building were tested by combining VSG and NDT to clearly identify their weak sections [19]. This simplified the use of structural reinforcements, which could be installed more accurately [20]. Riggio et al. [5] reported improvements in the estimation of physical-mechanical properties using NDT on Giotto's bell tower structure in Florence, Italy. The work of the COST Action IE0601 "Wood Science for Conservation of Cultural Heritage" (WoodCultHer) must also be mentioned. This was developed in 2007-2008 within the framework of the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST Actions). The Task Group "Assessment of Timber Structures" generated a document titled "Guidelines for On-Site Assessment of Historic Timber Structures" and gave rise to an interesting publication with the same title [21]. Guidelines are proposed for the evaluation of existing buildings by performing a highly structured analysis to provide enough data for proper structural safety analyses and planning interventions. This paper analyses timber pieces with emphasis on VSG. In addition, it gave rise to a pre-normative document prEN 17121 [22] and is currently being developed within the European Committee for Standardization, Technical Committee 346 "Conservation of Cultural Heritage" (CEN/TC 346) by its Working Group 10 "Historic Timber Structures" and has been launched for formal vote in 2019.

1.3 Cross-section variation

The study of timber members from existing buildings frequently reveals a highly variable cross-section (CS) along their length which is an important parameter for visual grading and mechanical behaviour [15,23,24]. This geometric variation can be caused by biotic degradation or irregularities in the sawing of the original pieces, and it may influence the estimation of mechanical properties [25,26]. The experimental procedure of geometric measurements may therefore have a relevant influence on the accuracy of the models obtained. Lourenço et al. [27] proposed a predictive model and a constant value for CS loss in softwood pieces from existing buildings. The proposed model was used to define deterioration curves over time, resulting in a predictive life-cycle time-dependent reliability index. Íñiguez-González et al. [28] observed that the coefficient of variation (CoV) of the cross section dimensions presented differences up to 4 or 5 times between old and new timber pieces. Sousa et al. [26] showed a 5% reduction in MOE_{dyn} and MOE_{sta} and a 30% reduction in compressive strength parallel to the grain between decayed and non-decayed parts in 20 old floor beams of *Castanea sativa* Mill. due to a variation in CS decay with NDT. However, the above research analyses the influence of CS from a different point of view from that of this paper. Nevado et al. [29] and the thesis by Nevado [30] use a more similar approach to that of the research works on structural reliability and its relationship with the variability of the section.

The aim of this work is to determine the influence of CS geometric variability in the estimation of bending stiffness using acoustic methods in the assessment of timber members from an 18th century building. Furthermore, several geometric measurement criteria were analysed in order to achieve a better prediction of MOE_{sta} based on NDT parameters.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Materials

The tested material comes from the Royal Coliseum of Charles III in Aranjuez, Madrid, Spain, designed by the French architect Jaime Marquet and built in 1768. This theatre was inaugurated in 1769 [31], one year before of theatre of the same name in San Lorenzo de El Escorial (1770). They are the two oldest roofed theatres in Spain still in use. The last restoration was undertaken in 1994, following the project of the architect Mariano Bayón Álvarez. The works were halted from 1996 to 2008. The structure of the roof was then disassembled and stored under cover, which made it possible to conserve many of its original pieces. The theatre reopened in 2014. The original main structure of the roof consisted of trusses with an approximate span of 18.40 m with a 32° slope. They were composed of 300x300 mm² CS truss rafters, 300x400 mm² ties with two double stop-splayed and tabled scarf joints, a king post, collar beam and two struts, Figure 1. The spacing between trusses was around 2.60 m and two intermediate purlins over the roof chord supported the rafters, with a 150x200 mm² CS, spaced at approximately 0.80 m and with a total length of 11.38 m, Figure 2. The ends of the rafters were supported on the ridge beam and on the sleeper at the eave, Figure 1. Twenty-one of these rafters are analyzed in this work. Although the main timber structure has been preserved, its main structural function has been transferred to a new steel structure.

The wood species was identified as Salzmann pine by the Forest Timber Industries Laboratory of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and the Structural Timber Laboratory of INIA-CIFOR (National Agricultural Research Institute), Madrid, Spain.

2.2 Piece marking

The specimens obtained from the original rafters were numbered from 1 to 21. Their length varied from 9.53 to 11.00 m after cutting the machined ends. The end nearest to the roof ridge was chosen as the origin. Several reference cross-sections (RCS) were marked on the specimens to measure their CS dimensions. The first reference cross-section (RCS0) was positioned at 20 cm from the origin and the following RCSs were at every two meters, Figure 3. As a result, the number of RCS varies from 5 to 6, depending on piece length.

2.3 CS measurement and nominal size

CS dimensions (thickness, *b* and width, *h*) were measured with Haglöf Mantax Blue 400 mm calliper to 1 mm of accuracy (Haglöf Sweden AB, Långsele, Sweden) in all RCS, Figure 4 (a). The calliper is used to measure the distance between two parallel faces, attaching one of the jaws of the apparatus on the flattest face and the other parallel jaw where it makes contact with the CS. This way of measuring provides a slightly larger area than the actual area of the part but is a simpler measurement method to perform on site Figure 4 (b, c).

A nominal cross-section (NCS) dimension has been assigned to each piece. Their dimensions were defined using three different criteria to obtain *b* and *h*, depending on the number of measurements taken, Figure 5: A) Average values of all RCS. This criterion shows the most representative average RCS, although it has the inconvenience of taking longer on *in-situ* assessment; B) Consideration of the central segment of the piece, with two options: B1) Values of only one CS dimension corresponding to RCS4; and B2) Average values of RCS4 and RCS6. The aim is to take only the dimensions of the segment where the bending moment is highest in simply supported pieces; C) Consideration of the extreme segment of the piece, with two options: C1) Values corresponding to the closest RCS to one of the ends of the piece (RCS0); and C2) Average values of RCS0 and RCS2. This criterion may be the easiest on-site measurement procedure in the assessment of floor joists. On the other hand, extreme CS are less relevant for the estimation of global bending stiffness. However, criterion C has been considered to quantify the increase in error when taking one or two measurements at one end of the piece compared with the other criteria.

2.4 Longitudinal vibration measurements

The longitudinal wave frequency determined by the acoustic resonance-based method was measured in each specimen. A Portable Lumber Grader (PLG) (Fakopp, Sopron, Hungary) with a non-contact sensor (microphone placed in front of one end) was used to conduct acoustic resonance longitudinal measurements on each specimen, Figure 6 (a). The frequency range of the PLG microphone is 100 - 15000 Hz. Each specimen was supported at two points near the ends during resonance measurement. A longitudinal wave was induced in the timber by hammer impact. The signal was recorded, and the first mode natural frequency (f) of the longitudinal wave signals was immediately obtained through the Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) program in the device. The sampling rate adopted in the longitudinal vibration measurements depends on piece length according to the expression $15000/L$ (Hz), where L is the piece length (m). In this work, with approximately 10 m long pieces, the sampling rate was 1500 Hz. In this case, the maximum frequency that can be measured is 750 Hz. The natural longitudinal frequency obtained in this work was between 194 and 262 Hz (average value 219 Hz) and it is far below the limit. The acoustic wave velocity (V) of each piece was then calculated using Eq. 1.

$$V = 2 f L \quad (1)$$

Where f is the longitudinal vibration frequency (in Hz) and L is the length of the specimen (in m), variable from 9.53 to 11.00 m.

2.5 Time-of-Flight (ToF) measurement

Three acoustic devices were used to obtain the Time-of-Flight (ToF): The MicroSecond Timer (MST) (Fakopp, Sopron, Hungary) with spike sensors, the Sylvatest Duo (SYL) (CBS-CBT, Lausanne, Switzerland) with conical 22 kHz sensors and the USLab (USL) (Agricef, Campinas, Brazil) with conical 45 kHz sensors, Figure 6 (b, c, d), respectively. The first is a stress-wave device and excitation is induced by means of a hammer. The last two devices are based on ultrasonic measurements and excitation is induced by a piezoelectric sensor. Average ToF data for each piece were obtained from two ToF measurements with the sensors in the upper and lower thirds of the piece end surfaces, Figure 7. These measurements are parallel to the main axis of the piece, and they are used to determine velocity (V) according to Eq. 2.

$$V = L / ToF_{mean} \quad (2)$$

Where L is the sensor distance (in m) and ToF_{mean} is the average ToF in each piece (in s).

The time-of-flight method has the advantage of being able to measure in-situ without disassembling the structure, unlike the longitudinal vibration method. Therefore, the time-of-flight method is more practical to use in building assessment.

2.6 Mechanical testing

The MOE_{sta} was obtained by bending test according to the EN 408 [32] standard procedure. The pieces were simply supported over a span of 10.00 m (except pieces No. 6 and 7 with 9.20 m span) placing the RCS0 on one of the supports. Two concentrated loads were applied at thirds of the span, and midspan deflection was recorded using a digital displacement measurement device with 0.01 mm accuracy, Figure 8. The maximum total load was 2.39 kN and maximum bending stress was 4.4 N mm^{-2} (2.7 due to applied load and 1.7 due to self-weight) considering an average CS of $150 \times 200 \text{ mm}^2$. This stress is much lower than the bending strength of this timber, and it is clearly within the elastic behaviour of the piece.

2.7 Density and Moisture Content (MC)

Density (ρ) was obtained as mass divided by volume, using the actual CS area of a 100 mm long slice free of knots and resin pockets, as specified in EN 408 [32], Figure 4 (c). Two slices were cut from each piece, one close to RCS2 and the other close to RCS8. Piece density was calculated as the mean of both slice density values. The average density of the batch was 522 kg m^{-3} , and the coefficient of variation (CoV) was 7%. Piece No. 8 was not considered due to its

high resin content. MC was measured by the oven dry method according to the EN 13183-1 [33] standard using the density slices, with an average value of 13.7%.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 CS nominal size

The CS varies along the length of each piece. Table 1 (criterion A) shows the average dimensions and CoV for the 6 RCSs of the 21 rafters. The CoV is high as is common in old timber structures. The width (h) varies less than the thickness (b), at 3% and 11%, respectively. This is probably due to the need for a uniform upper level of the roofing.

In order to verify the service limit state of the structure, a nominal size may be assigned to each piece. The nominal size should be the most representative CS in the whole deformation behaviour of the piece; the criteria described in section 2.3 “CS Measurement and nominal size” were used for this. Table 1 shows the nominal size dimensions (b_n and h_n) of the 21 rafters obtained according to the 3 different criteria defined in Section 2.3, together with the moment of inertia (I) CoV.

The expression for I contains parameters b_n and h_n , and it will affect MOE_{sta} determination. The ANOVA and mean tests were therefore carried out for I using the different criteria to define nominal size, concluding that there are no significant differences in I using either of the criteria, with a 95% confidence interval (CI), Figure 9, although there are differences in variability. In criterion A there is a higher concentration of data around the mean value than in the cases where other criteria are used.

3.2 Wave transmission velocity

The average velocity (V) of wave transmission for the 21 pieces was 4649, 4926, 4905 and 5291 $m\ s^{-1}$, with CoV of 4, 4, 4 and 6% for PLG, MST, SYL and USL, respectively. The value obtained with the ultrasonic device USL is slightly higher than the one obtained with the stress wave device, as was shown in previous works [34,35]. However, the velocity obtained with SYL is practically equal to MST results. Research by Llana et al. [36] similar results were obtained with the same devices, where MST results were slightly higher than SYL. The ratio between the velocities obtained with ultrasound (USL) and stress wave (MST) is 1.07. This ratio had a mean value of 1.11 in Spruce [37], and 1.07 (1.06-1.09) in larger CS pieces of 4 coniferous species [34]. The lowest velocity was obtained by the longitudinal vibration method (PLG).

3.3 Modulus of elasticity

The MOE_{sta} depends on the I, which may be calculated using different criteria to define the nominal size of the piece (criteria A, B and C), and the MOE_{dyn} was obtained according to Eq. 3. Table 2 shows the average values and CoV, of MOE_{dyn} and MOE_{sta} for each device.

$$MOE_{dyn} = V_i^2 \rho \quad (3)$$

Where V_i is the velocity obtained with the different devices (V_{PLG} , V_{MST} , V_{SYL} and V_{USL}) in $m\ s^{-1}$ and ρ is the density in $kg\ m^{-3}$.

Linear regression was established between the MOE_{sta} and MOE_{dyn} , depending on the different criteria adopted to define NCS size of pieces and according to Eq. 4.

$$MOE_{sta} = a + b MOE_{dyn} \quad (4)$$

Where a (in $N\ mm^{-2}$) and b are the regression coefficients shown in Table 2.

The best results were obtained with criterion A for the longitudinal vibration procedure ($r^2 = 0.87$ and standard error $StE = 579 \text{ N mm}^{-2}$) and criterion B for the ToF procedures ($r^2 = 0.72-0.78$ and $StE = 683-720 \text{ N mm}^{-2}$) with no differences between criteria B1 and B2. The best prediction with criteria B can be explained because the maximum bending moment is situated in the central third of the span, where NCS was obtained. The different behavior in case of longitudinal vibration (PLG) can be explained because Eq. 1 derives velocity from natural frequency and is valid for constant CS pieces, and nominal size in criterion A gives a CS closer to the theoretical constant CS. Finally, the poorest prediction was obtained with criterion C1 where the StE is around four times greater than it is for criterion B.

In other research works, the r^2 obtained for each device obtain similar results with different species. Some results are compared below, and unless otherwise indicated, the regressions were established to estimate MOE_{sta} from MOE_{dyn} . In the ultrasound method, Arriaga et al. [38] showed $r^2 = 0.42 - 0.74$ in 82 new sawn Missanda timber (*Erythrophleum ivorense* A. Chev., *Erythrophleum suaveolens* Brenan) pieces with $80 \times 80 \times 1600$ and $200 \times 250 \times 5000 \text{ mm}^3$ using SYL. Machado and Palma [11] obtained $r^2 = 0.76$ with PUNDIT plus (Proceq, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland) with flat contact 150 kHz transducers. The material tested was defect-free timber with $40 \times 100 \times 2000 \text{ mm}^3$ dimensions. Teder et al. [39] showed $r^2 = 0.37$ with end-to-end transmission velocities recorded with the Tico ultrasonic instrument (Proceq, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland) in 92 newly sawn Norway spruce pieces. Arriaga et al. [34] showed $r^2 = 0.85$ with SYL and the same with USL in 120 timber pieces (30 pieces of each species of radiata, Scots, Salzmann and maritime pine) measuring $90 \times 140 \times 4000 \text{ mm}^3$. Arriaga et al. [37] reported $r^2 = 0.68, 0.74, 0.86$ with USL with 22 and 45 kHz conical sensors and MST, respectively. The specimens used were twelve large CS Norway spruce pieces from a 19th century building measuring $76 \times 226 \times 4520 \text{ mm}^3$. Using the stress-wave method, Arriaga et al. [34,37] obtained $r^2 = 0.81$ and $r^2 = 0.86$ with MST, respectively, and in the same pieces described above for each research work. Using the longitudinal vibration method, Arriaga et al. [40] showed $r^2 = 0.87$ in 150 radiata pine sawn timber measuring $80 \times 120 \times 2500 \text{ mm}^3$.

A bootstrapping test was carried out with R programming and the boot package [41–43] to compare the accuracy of the MOE_{sta} estimation of each geometric criterion. According to Bayesian statistics, accuracy is inversely proportional to variance. Bootstrapping methods are computer-intensive methods of statistical analysis, which use resampling to assign measures of accuracy. Furthermore, this method is used to get closer to parameters such as StE , bias, variance, CI and others that are used in statistical analysis. A bootstrapping test was chosen in this work because the criterion C MOE_{sta} variable did not display normality and there were few samples. This made it impossible to use an ANOVA test.

Figure 10 shows the average value of the StE of 100 bootstrap tests with 10^6 replicates. The StE obtained in criteria A and B are the lowest, while criterion C has the highest values. Criteria C1 and C2 are therefore not recommended in the assessment procedure. B1, B2 and A are the most accurate criteria.

On the other hand, it must be taken into account that in the structural verification of bending members the deformation limitation is the critical factor and bending strength is usually not exhausted. For this reason, the load carrying capacity is usually directly dependent on stiffness ($MOE \cdot I$). However, this does not mean that the strength criterion should not be checked. The prediction of strength in existing structures is less accurate than stiffness prediction, and this should be studied in depth in future work.

4. Conclusions

Cross-section variability in the thickness, b , was more pronounced than it was in the width, h , with a CoV of 11 and 3%, respectively. Geometric variation is common in pieces from old

timber structures, and a criterion is needed to define the NCS of pieces to achieve a more accurate bending stiffness estimation (or the equivalent modulus of elasticity).

The ratios between the velocities obtained with the four NDT devices are similar to those described in previous works that used shorter pieces (3-4 m vs 10 m), except in the case of the SYL and MST devices.

The most suitable criterion to assign a NCS to each piece was deduced in this work by comparing NDT with mechanical bending test results. The average MOE_{sta} values obtained with the three criteria proposed to define NCS show a CoV in criteria A and B from 15 to 16%, and in criterion C from 22 to 31%. On the other hand, the average MOE_{dyn} values have a CoV from 11 to 16%, which is closer to criteria A and B. Criterion C is the least accurate, as can be seen in the bootstrap test. Furthermore, the linear regressions between MOE_{sta} and MOE_{dyn} showed a StE in A and B criteria around 3-4 times lower than in the C criterion, which supports the rejection of criterion C.

Finally, in order to verify the service limit state of bending timber members it is recommended to establish the NCS by applying the B criterion when MOE is estimated by means of ToF-based devices (ultrasound and stress waves). Criterion A is proposed for MOE estimation by vibration-based devices. This last case is less frequent in the assessment of existing timber structures because it requires vibration-free conditions.

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Figure captions and description:

(Colour and 2-column fitting) Figure 1. Roof trusses and details of rafter ends.

(Colour and 1-column fitting) Figure 2. 18th century rafter timber pieces tested.

(Black and white and 2-column fitting) Figure 3. Explanatory drawing of the layout of the RCS marking, the position, and numbering of the faces and edges of a piece.

(Colour and 1-column fitting) Figure 4. Example of apparent CS measurement with calliper (a), apparent area with calliper (b) and the actual CS area of the scanned slice (c).

(Black and white and 1-column fitting) Figure 5. RCS criterion diagram.

(Colour and 2-column fitting) Figure 6. PLG device, longitudinal vibration method (a), MicroSecond Timer stress-wave device (b), Sylvatest Duo ultrasound device (c), USLab ultrasound device (d).

(Colour and 2-column fitting) Figure 7. Sensor placement.

(Colour and 1-column fitting) Figure 8. Bending mechanical testing arrangement.

(Black and white and 1-column fitting) Figure 9. ANOVA and mean tests for moment of inertia for each criterion.

(Black and white and 1-column fitting) Figure 10. Results of the average bootstrapping standard error for each criterion of 100 bootstrap tests with 10^6 replicas.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Table 1. Average CS dimensions of the 21 pieces and nominal sizes according to different criteria.

Piece	Nominal size (NCS)										
	Criterion A		Criterion B				Criterion C				
	b _n - CoV (mm - %)	h _n - CoV (mm - %)	B1		B2		C1		C2		
			b _n (mm)	h _n (mm)							
1	167 - 6	194 - 5	169	199	170	198	163	191	172	192	
2	131 - 7	199 - 4	133	203	133	204	115	187	121	198	
3	148 - 3	187 - 1	151	185	150	186	147	188	150	188	
4	156 - 4	194 - 8	160	182	157	181	165	212	162	203	
5	168 - 2	190 - 1	166	191	167	190	169	194	167	192	
6	127 - 2	192 - 3	123	188	125	188	130	194	129	191	
7	155 - 6	192 - 10	162	203	160	206	138	163	149	173	
8	139 - 8	195 - 4	122	197	135	200	136	180	136	191	
9	130 - 1	201 - 4	129	199	131	199	127	194	130	194	
10	148 - 4	200 - 4	146	208	147	207	146	191	146	199	
11	171 - 4	190 - 3	180	185	173	187	168	200	168	195	
12	160 - 3	193 - 1	163	196	163	194	153	194	154	195	
13	141 - 2	197 - 1	141	196	140	196	137	195	140	197	
14	171 - 4	195 - 1	175	199	176	196	169	194	172	196	
15	188 - 2	198 - 2	189	198	188	200	184	193	186	196	
16	148 - 12	196 - 5	172	204	163	205	134	200	147	199	
17	143 - 8	196 - 3	156	202	156	202	123	197	132	198	
18	150 - 8	192 - 2	149	192	147	189	164	192	163	192	
19	149 - 5	205 - 4	144	211	142	212	154	204	155	207	
20	133 - 8	197 - 3	122	202	123	201	136	194	133	198	
21	138 - 2	181 - 6	144	183	141	177	136	195	138	193	
CoV _n (%)	b-h	11	3	13	4	12	5	12	5	12	3
	I	12		17		17		21		15	

b_n, h_n: nominal size thickness and width of the piece according to different criteria;
CoV: CoV of b and h along the piece;
CoV_i: CoV of b, h and I of the 21 pieces.

Table 2. MOE_{sta} (MOE_A , MOE_{B1} , MOE_{C1} for each criterion) and MOE_{dyn} (MOE_{PLG} , MOE_{MST} , MOE_{SYL} , MOE_{USL} for each device) average values and linear regressions (Eq. 4) summary.

		MOE_{PLG}/CoV	MOE_{MST}/CoV	MOE_{SYL}/CoV	MOE_{USL}/CoV
		11582/16	12969/12	12855/11	14954/11
MOE_A/CoV	a	180	-936	-1870	-2036
	b	0.8108	0.8102	0.8900	0.7761
	r^2	0.87	0.66	0.70	0.71
	StE	579	946	889	870
9571/16					
MOE_{B1}/CoV	a	3393	-360	-715	-821
	b	0.5010	0.7368	0.7709	0.6698
	r^2	0.46	0.75	0.72	0.73
	StE	1007	683	720	711
9195/15					
MOE_{B2}/CoV	a	2795	-1033	-1497	-1553
	b	0.5621	0.7971	0.8403	0.7261
	r^2	0.51	0.78	0.76	0.76
	StE	1017	687	713	714
9305/15					
MOE_{C1}/CoV	a	-4263	-2241	-3961	-4652
	b	1.2590	0.9689	1.1112	1.0015
	r^2	0.52	0.23	0.27	0.29
	StE	2258	2850	2782	2737
10324/31					
MOE_{C2}/CoV	a	-1476	-989	-2347	-2758
	b	0.9673	0.8263	0.9392	0.8349
	r^2	0.65	0.36	0.41	0.43
	StE	1304	1775	1705	1670
9727/22					
MOE_i and the standard error (StE) in N mm⁻² and CoV in %.					